

FROM STAC TO POLICY SUPPORT USING THE JRC BIG DATA ANALYTICS PLATFORM

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ABSTRACT

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission is committed to providing independent, evidence-based science and knowledge that supports European Union policies. To facilitate this, the JRC has developed the Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP), a data platform that allows data scientists to easily access, analyse, view, and reuse scientific data to generate and communicate evidence-based insights and foresight. BDAP hosts mainly spatiotemporal data at petabyte scale from various domains and it recently adopted and implemented the Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification to describe its data. BDAP reuses and benefits from various STAC Free and Open Source software and tools from the STAC ecosystem. This paper will showcase concrete examples of this ecosystem in action together with its insights, foresight and impact on EU policies.

Index Terms— Big Data, STAC, spatio-temporal data, data-cube, analysis ready data

1. INTRODUCTION

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission is committed to providing independent, evidence-based science and knowledge that supports EU policies. To facilitate this, the JRC has developed the Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP), an on premises cloud platform providing JRC scientists the necessary data and data-services within a shared and collaborative environment [1]. BDAP provides JRC researchers with a shared data analytics ecosystem to easily access, analyse, view, and reuse scientific data in order to generate and communicate evidence-based insights and foresight. Research findings based on the exploitation of big data from space have a direct impact on a range of EU policies, in particular for those related to climate change, crisis management, and sustainable development.

2. DATA MANAGEMENT IN BDAP

BDAP retrieves terabytes of data per day from various providers and domains, based on users' needs. These data undergo a series of quality checks performed by reusable micro-services. Depending on the provider and on the type

Fig. 1: Data flow in BDAP.

of data retrieved, an ingestion workflow is designed by assembling the necessary micro-services. Once data are considered valid, they are stored on EOS (EOS Open Storage), an open-source distributed file system developed by CERN [2], directly coupled with processing nodes in order to avoid any bottleneck. In case STAC-compliant metadata [3] are not already provided from the data source, they are automatically generated through transformations from existing metadata standards (e.g., OGC GeoJSON, INSPIRE) or by extracting metadata from the data itself (e.g., geographical metadata from GeoTiff). Finally, metadata are stored in an Elasticsearch [4] instance. Users are provided with standard STAC REST APIs, built on stac-fastapi, enabling data discovery for further analysis. The data flow of BDAP is illustrated in Fig. 1.

BDAP hosts a vast collection of spatiotemporal data from various domains reaching almost 15 petabytes. To effectively describe these data, BDAP has recently implemented the Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification, which was chosen among other standards (e.g. OGC, INSPIRE) for its modularity, flexibility to adapt to different domains, and wide adoption in the EO community. Each dataset can be described with its own set of STAC extensions while sharing common mandatory fields with the rest of the data. Figure 2 shows an example of two different BDAP datasets benefiting of the modularity of the STAC standard.

The flexibility of this standard is leveraged by the flexibility of the NoSQL database Elasticsearch. Through the use of templates, Elasticsearch enables the creation of mul-

Fig. 2: Example of BDAP data description through STAC standard.

multiple data indexes sharing common core fields while differing in domain-specific fields. Consequently, queries can be performed across all indexes simultaneously using an index pattern, retrieving relevant records from all associated indexes. The resulting set of records may provide varying levels of detail depending on the specific Elasticsearch index from which they were extracted [5]. Importantly though, all the complexities involved in managing the Elasticsearch indexes are hidden from the users, who can simply utilise the STAC APIs without being burdened by technical details.

The adoption of the STAC standard extends beyond its flexibility. It is in fact supported by a comprehensive STAC ecosystem [6] including libraries, tools, and clients that can be readily utilised for accessing and processing data. The next section showcases concrete examples of this ecosystem in action.

3. FROM STAC TO POLICY SUPPORT

Open data combined with open source software can contribute to transparent and reproducible results, leveraging reliable and sound scientific research. Following the example of the opening of the USGS Landsat archive in 2008, the Copernicus program of the European Union adopted the free and open data policy. As a result, a wealth of Earth Observation data is now open and freely accessible. A plethora of open source software libraries to process and analyse geospatial data has been available for some time. However, a standardised access to these data was lacking until recently. Geospatial datasets are typically large in size and therefore difficult to transfer in (data ingress) or out (data egress). They are processed most efficiently in the data centre where they are stored. Without a standard in place, cloud services providing geospatial data access and processing capabilities implemented customised APIs. This hampered interoperability, with the risk of vendor lock-in to the users.

STAC is being adopted by numerous big data from space ecosystems and platforms such as the Copernicus Data Space

Ecosystem (CDSE) [7] or Microsoft Planetary Computer [8], so that a standardised access to the data can be provided, completing the missing piece in the ecosystem of open source and inter-operable geospatial data analysis tools.

3.1. From STAC to data cubes

The PySTAC-client [9] Python library allows one to discover data collection items, based on acquisition time and geographical region of interest. Currently, over nine million items are stored in BDAP (see Fig. 3). These items can be filtered based on their attributes, including those defined in the Earth Observation (EO) STAC extension such as cloud cover (see Fig. 2). The data items resulting from the search can then be organised into objects that represent a time series of geospatial data, a *data cube*. Users of the BDAP can use various libraries from the STAC ecosystem to create data cubes. As an example, the `odc-stac` [10] library uses the Open Data Cube (ODC) [11, 12] model to load the discovered STAC items into a Python `xarray` [13]. Data cubes structured in an `xarray` can then be processed either locally or in a parallel distributed computing cluster using `Dask` [14].

3.2. From data cubes to ARD

Sentinel-2, part of the Copernicus programme, is an optical multi-spectral satellite imaging instrument with a minimum revisit frequency of five days. It acquires images in 13 spectral bands: four bands at 10 m, six bands at 20 m and three bands at 60 m spatial resolution. Currently, the Sentinel-2 collection represents the majority of the STAC items stored in BDAP.

STAC-compliant metadata are generated as part of the data ingestion workflow. As described in the previous section, data is represented to the user as multi-temporal and multi-spectral data cubes via open source libraries. Following the principles of Analysis Ready Datasets (ARD) [15], these data cubes should be organised into a form that enables immediate analysis with a minimum of additional user effort.

Fig. 3: Number of BDAP STAC metadata items that can be discovered through STAC APIs.

Fig. 4: Surface reflectance for spectral bands B4 (red) and B8 (near infrared) including both clear and masked (detected as cloud or shadow) observations. Interpolated version of the surface reflectance observations.

However, immediate analysis of the data cubes, for instance to monitor vegetation dynamics, is hampered by atmospheric perturbations that cause both gaps and noise in the time series. Therefore, a gap filling and smoothing operation is commonly applied. In [16], a surface reflectance time series reconstruction method (RTSR) is presented. Smoothed values of surface reflectance values are adjusted to approach the trustworthy observations, using a vegetation index as a proxy for reliability. This method has been implemented using the open source pyjeo [17] Python library and runs in the BDAP cluster in a Docker container.

3.3. From ARD to policy support

The ARD can be used to obtain relevant insight and foresight in the different domains where the JRC provides EU policy support. Ongoing research uses ARD to automatically delineate crop fields [18] (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Parcel delineation (red) from Sentinel-2 imagery (top). Reference parcels (bottom) extracted from the open data portal of the Dutch government [19].

Another application is on drought monitoring. A classification method was developed that is based on a random forest. It uses ARD based on Sentinel-2 imagery to detect water (see Fig. 6). Researchers can present their results to policy makers in the form of dashboards. These dashboards can be published securely via dedicated service named Voilà as a Service (VaaS).

Fig. 6: Water classification algorithm used for drought monitoring based on Sentinel-2 images (top). A random forest detects water (shown in yellow in the bottom image).

4. CONCLUSION

Adopting the STAC specification in the JRC catalog leveraged the use of geospatial data, such as those coming from the Copernicus programme like Sentinel-2. A diverse ecosystem of open source libraries and tools can be readily used to interact with the data as a basis to generate and communicate evidence-based insights and foresight at the policy level. The case studies that have been shown here are just a few examples of applications. A standardized access to the data is only a first but important step in making the processing work flows reproducible and inter-operable, which will be the focus of future work.

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